

DIGITIZATION AS A FACTOR IN THE FORMATION OF NEW ECONOMIC TECHNOLOGIES IN COMPETITIVE CONDITIONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the basics of the development and effectiveness of digitalization, as well as the basic principles and factors in the formation of new economic technologies.

Keywords: Digitalization, digital economy, digital technologies, information and communication technology, innovation.

In the process of modernizing the economy in a competitive environment, the development of market mechanisms of existence, including the reduction of government intervention in economic processes, necessitate an active state policy on digitalization. The very concept of “digitalization” indicates a new stage in improving the management of the production of goods and services and production itself based on the “end-to-end” use of modern IT, from the Internet of Things to e-government technologies. Digitalization is nothing more than a transition from analogue to digital. This process involves not only replacing production tools, but also introducing analytical systems to make production as profitable as possible. One of the basic reasons for the expansion of the digital segment of the economy is the growth of the transaction sector. This sector includes public administration, finance, wholesale and retail trade, as well as the provision of various utility, personal and social services. The introduction of information and communication technologies in public administration, education, healthcare and agriculture, in particular, the improvement of the e-government system and the further development of the domestic market for software products and information technologies are identified [1], as a priority for the further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

New social models of interaction based on the combination of modern information platforms lead to the practical implementation of new economic technologies (NETs). By them, in our opinion, we mean a set of fundamentally new data processing tools and methods “embedded” in organizational management systems, combined into integral technological platforms for the purposeful creation, transmission, storage and display of an information product (data, ideas, knowledge) and ensuring maximum reduction of transaction costs for the interaction of economic agents. The basic principles of NETs are as follows:

- development of fundamentally new business models;
- optimal combination of various information technologies and methods of their use in organizational and technological processes of the real sector of the economy;
- minimization of transaction costs and material resources used in production.

NETs are developed on the basis of modern information technologies and in accordance with real economic conditions. If earlier production, trade, and financial technologies were consistently developing, then by now NETs have emerged, which are the basis of the modern information economy, based on predominantly horizontal interactions, innovative entrepreneurship, information engineering and auto-formalization of economic processes [2]. The material basis of NET is represented by data centers and modern IT platforms for systematization and analytical processing of information.

The post-industrial economy has played an important role in defining the rules of telecommunications, establishing technical standards, supporting research and innovation, which, in turn, contributed to the emergence of a new sector of the innovation economy – the digital market. Therefore, the modern digital revolution is largely driven by market and technological innovation [3]. Currently, there is a digital revolution based on the creation of global industrial networks using artificial intelligence, the widespread spread of the Internet of Things, the spread of automatic identification services, the collection and processing of global databases, cloud services, the development of social networks and various platforms and services in the digital environment of the Internet. , contributes to the development of traditional branches of public administration and, in particular, information and communication technologies and their application are becoming a major part of modern management systems in all sectors of the economy. The term “digital economy” (its author is Nicholas Negroponte) appeared relatively recently, in 1995. This concept is associated with the intensive development of information and communication technologies (ICT), the beginning of the second generation informatization process, which is the basis of the emerging VI technological order. In fact, all spheres of human life (economic, social, political, cultural, social and others) have changed to one degree or another thanks to the discovery and development of ICT [4]. The electronic information revolution in the economy has significantly influenced the transformation of economic relations for more than four decades. Transformations in industrial relations and institutions are

occurring both in content and form. In the digital economy, economic relations as subject-object ones become more complicated when they are supplemented with certain algorithms. The specificity of transformations in production and economic relations is reflected in the fact that the processes of production, distribution, exchange and consumption (use) of information become the main ones in comparison with other types of economic and economic activities and influence them.

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